

Kamilova Nargiza Abdukakhorovna
Phd in economics associate professor
Samarkand institute of economy and service
The Republic of Uzbekistan

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PROBLEMS OF INTERNATIONALIZATION OF MODERN HIGHER EDUCATION

Abstract. *This article reveals the issues of internationalization of the higher education system, improving its quality, and the introduction of international training standards. At the same time, the process of internationalization of higher education, along with advantages, carries some problematic nuances, the solution of which requires a competent approach through the prism of international cooperation.*

Keywords: *globalization, higher education, international training standards, internationalization of higher education, credit-modular education system, the international cooperation.*

Introduction. Today, more and more countries are actively participating in the process of internationalization of higher education, and how successfully they can use world experience will depend on the level of development of the national higher education system. Uzbekistan is no exception, the republic is taking large-scale measures to internationalize higher education, improve its quality, and introduce international training standards. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further development of the higher education system" of April 20, 2017, was adopted and the Program for the integrated development of the higher education system for the period 2017-2021 was approved with a volume of funds of about 1.7 trillion soum, as well as the Concept development of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 with a roadmap for its implementation,

Purpose. The main goals set in these documents are the cardinal improvement of the higher education system in Uzbekistan, a radical revision of the content of training programs, and its approximation to the level of international standards.

To achieve this goal, the country's higher educational institutions have been set priority tasks, which include: improving the qualifications of the teaching staff of universities; creation of new curricula, modern educational and methodological literature for various areas of education; gradual transfer of the educational process to a credit-modular system: development of a methodology for calculating credits, taking into account the experience of the EU and ECTS, establishing the possibility of students choosing academic disciplines by analogy with EU universities; wide participation of the teaching staff and students of the republic in foreign exchange programs and trainings; inviting foreign teachers and professors to work in universities of the republic in order to improve

the educational process and exchange experience; ensuring the publication of articles by professors-teachers, scientific applicants, doctoral students, undergraduate and graduate students in authoritative international scientific journals of the Scopus and Web of Science databases, increasing the citation rates of articles, as well as the gradual inclusion of republican scientific journals in the international scientific and technical data base; ensuring the academic independence of universities; increasing the investment attractiveness of higher education, attracting foreign educational and scientific technologies, creating technology parks and start-ups in universities; improving the infrastructure and material and technical base of universities, including through the widespread attraction of concessional funds from international financial institutions, the gradual transfer of universities to a self-financing system, and ensuring their financial stability [1];

To implement the set tasks, the higher education of Uzbekistan is actively developing international cooperation. Thus, joint educational institutions are being created, foreign lecturers and scientists are involved in the process of education in the universities of the republic: academic mobility of both teachers and students is developing; joint research activities are carried out, international conferences are organized on topical issues in the field of higher education, information technology, resource, and energy conservation.

These measures made it possible to significantly increase the number of universities in the republic. If in 2016 the number of universities was 70, today their number has reached 93[2], 19 of them are branches of foreign universities. Among them are Westminster International University, Singapore Institute for Management Development, Turin Polytechnic University, Inha University, Adju University, a branch of the Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, a branch of Lomonosov Moscow State University, a branch of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas named after I. M. Gubkina and others. Universities of Uzbekistan, working side by side with branches of foreign universities, adopt advanced teaching technologies, progressive methods of management; teachers have the opportunity to work and improve their qualifications in these universities.

Credit mobility is one of the important measures for the development of international cooperation. Student mobility in Uzbekistan is carried out within the framework of the political, economic, and academic interuniversity partnership, as well as on their initiative, students can enter foreign universities. Also, the mobility of students and teachers of Uzbekistan is carried out within the framework of international programs, such as the TEMPUS and ERASMUS + programs, organized within the Bologna Process of the European Union, the Fulbright student exchange program in the USA, DAAD Germany, the program of the German Society for International Cooperation GIZ, the Chevening Program of Great Britain. , educational exchange programs of the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science, and Technology (MEXT) of Japan, as well as various programs of China, Spain.

Thanks to these programs, hundreds of teachers and students of Uzbekistan have the opportunity to get acquainted with advanced international experience in the higher

education system, acquire new knowledge and skills, and improve their qualifications in leading universities in the world. This will help improve the statistics of scientific activities in Uzbekistan. According to statistics of 2017, Uzbekistan ranked 99th in the world in terms of published articles in the Web of Science database [3].

I would especially like to note that during the first Uzbek-Russian educational forum held in the city of Tashkent in October 2019 under the motto "New personnel for a new economy", the universities of Uzbekistan and Russia signed about 130 agreements and contracts. Under these agreements, specific "road maps" have been developed for the creation of branches and joint educational programs.

Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service (SamIES) is one of the universities actively implementing these transformations. The Institute, being the only university in the republic specializing in the training of economic personnel for the service sector, actively implements double degree programs with foreign universities. So, starting from the 2019-2020 academic year, the institute has been implementing joint training programs with the Kazan Federal University and with the Vladimir State University in the educational direction of "trade". In the future, the institute plans to organize training under double degree programs with the Tambov and Kuban State Universities, with which a memorandum of personnel exchange and relevant agreements have already been signed.

SamIES, like many other universities in Uzbekistan, participates in the Tempus and Erasmus + programs. So in recent years, within the framework of these programs, such projects have been implemented as UQASE - the Uzbek system of quality assurance in higher education, PERSEUS - Creation of publicly useful universities on the principle of "Research-Science-Production", QAPD - Improvement of the system of quality assurance in education through the professional development of academic leaders, UZDOC - Improving the quality of doctoral studies in universities of Uzbekistan, CANEM I and CANEM II - Central Asian Network of Economics and Management, KA 107 - International Credit Mobility (the University of Granada and University of Las Palmas), Great Silk Road - Peoples Friendship University of Russia, DECIDE - Development of services for people with disabilities [1].

The Institute has agreements on cooperation with 32 foreign universities in Spain, Belgium, Czech Republic, Russia, India, Indonesia, and other countries, following which joint conferences are held, online lectures are organized, student and teacher exchanges are organized.

Conclusion. The study of the organization of international cooperation of universities in Uzbekistan made it possible to highlight the main problems they face. This is, first of all, a low level of knowledge of a foreign language, primarily English and Russian, by teachers and students, which makes it difficult for them to actively participate in the process of academic exchange. Language barriers hinder effective communication when the interlocutors do not share a common language to communicate. To solve this problem, continuous systematic training of students and teachers in English and Russian is required. In our opinion, the participation of a foreign teacher and foreign students in the educational process of the institute can be effective.

An important problem is the lack of experience and low competence of teachers, doctoral students, students in the development and implementation of joint international scientific, technical, educational projects. To solve this problem, it is necessary to organize a continuous system of advanced training in innovative technologies in the scientific field. It should also be noted that teachers have insufficient experience in ensuring the compatibility of educational programs with partner universities, the lack of a developed system for recalculating and accumulating credit units. Research shows that international cooperation is complex and not easy to achieve or sustain in a short time. From our point of view, the preparation for international cooperation is influenced by factors such as competence and technological level, as well as behavior, values, and trust that need to be developed to achieve internationalization; low motivation of the teaching staff in the development of educational programs for foreign partners or, to put it another way, the resistance of teachers against institutional changes; slow assimilation of knowledge by the education system in the rapid flow of information.

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